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**PROBLEMS OF DRY CONTINENTAL WATER AND SOLUTIONS FOR DRY
CONTINENTAL (ARAL) POPULATION**

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Annotation: Provision of population with clean quality water is one of the most urgent and global problems today. The article shows the provision of quality water to the population of arid continental regions, the reasons for the sharp reduction of water resources in the region, the destruction of ecology, as well as the results of water quality analysis.

Key words: water resources, climate change, economic development, fresh water shortages, water level, ecological and hygienic assessment of water supply,

Entrance: There are a number of unsolved problems related to provision of population with quality drinking water, rational and efficient production, delivery and realization of drinking water. At present, ecological and hygienic assessment of water supply, maintenance of water quality at a constant level is one of the urgent problems in our country[1]. At the same time, water remains one of the main factors of socio-economic development of Central Asia. The water level of the Aral Sea for the last quarter of a century has decreased more than 15 times, the water level has fallen to 29 meters, 5.5 million hectares of salty sand have been formed on the territory, and as a consequence, the environment, human life and animal life are irreparably damaged. The annual volume of water resources in Central Asia is about 116 km³. 80 percent of water resources are used for agriculture, almost 7-8 percent for industry, and the rest for domestic, service and other purposes[2,3,4]. The environmental consequences of indiscriminate use of water in the region are well known. In addition, salinization and land and water crises have become an ongoing problem that threatens the stability of the economies of the region. Due to expected climate change, the region may face severe water shortages, accounting for 8-10% of current water consumption. The level of water supply to the region's population will decrease from the existing 2,500 m² to 1,400 m² per year.

The volume of freshwater use has increased 17-fold over a period when the land population has increased 3-fold. Moreover, according to some forecasts, the demand for fresh water may increase 3 times in 20 years. The problem of fresh water shortage is not alien to Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan ranks 25th in the list of countries with water deficit problems. Over the last 10 years, water reserves in Uzbekistan have decreased by 12% compared to last year by 15%. Consistent implementation of important programs and projects on development of the drinking water supply system in the Republic of Uzbekistan allows to radically improve the situation with centralized water supply in cities and districts, including rural areas.

There are several legal norms on this issue in our republic: Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures on social protection of population in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm province and mitigation of water deficit consequences", Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On water and water use.", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the level of drinking water supply to the population" Decree, UzDAVST 950:2011 "On measures to improve the management of water resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to increase and improve its quality"[5]. Hygienic requirements and water quality control", UzDAST 951:2011 "Centralized sources of drinking domestic water supply. Hygienic technical requirements and selection rules", 215 CMC 2.04.02-97 "Water supply. External network and equipment". Infectious and parasitic diseases occupy the first place among the population diseases related to water supply.

Experts from the World Health Organization have found that 80 percent of all diseases in the world are transmitted through contaminated water. According to the UN, about 3 billion people on earth use poor quality drinking water. As a result, infectious and non-communicable diseases spread among